

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 – GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D1.4: Pilot Sites Recycled Products Application

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Table - List of Deliverables (M1: January 2023)

NUM	DELIVERABLE NAME	TYPE	SHORT DESCRIPTION	LEAD PARTICIPANT	DISSEM IN ACTION LEVEL**	DUE DATE
D1.1	Collection of data, processing technologies	R	A database and a report on collected information (production, characteristics, and localisation data, together with representative processing technologies).	POLITO	PU	M9
D1.2	Characterization of waste and new products from Mineral and bio-organic waste.	DB	A database reporting the characteristics of the investigated mineral and organic waste and (recycled) products obtained after treatment activities (described in T1.3) will be delivered. Together with it, an operative manual to populate and fill the database will be also produced.	UNITO	PU	M22
D1.3	Treatment and processing activities for mineral and bio-organic waste	R	A report on the investigated treatment activities (methodologies, procedures, limits, etc.) will be produced.	UNITO	PU	M24
D1.4	Pilot Sites Recycled Products Application	R	Pilot sites to test and validate the proposed technologies will be assessed	UNITO	PU	M32

Table - List of Project Milestones

MILESTONE NUMBER	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK MODULES	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
MS1.1	Treatment Activities for EQW, CDW, EW	1	12	Planning and authorisation delivered
MS1.2	Data collection and processing of EQW, CDW, EW, CW	1	12	Collection of data and processing info for LCA within the due date (LCA linked to RM6)
MS1.3	Pilot Sites testing activities	1	18	Planning and authorisation delivered
MS1.4	Recycled Products Application (from MW/OBW)	1	24	Planning and authorisation delivered

A) Main objectives achieved

A. The application of the EoW and the by-product regulation to the pilot cases specifically analysed.

B. Hypothesis of application of Ministerial Decree 127/2024 to pilot cases:

- Production of technosols;
- Operational Process for Circular Plasters Experimentation;
- Enforced Embankment for civil applications;
- Reuse of fired ceramic scraps into the traditional ceramic production.

C. Analysis of the CE marking in particular with reference to the construction products and aggregates recovered.

D. The insights contained in this document relating to the building EoW represent the basis for the drafting of Guidelines for operators in the building EoW sector.

B) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT

In the activity of Task D1.4 the working Team, starting from the analysis of the operative protocols described in Deliverable D1.3 relating to the treatment and processing activities carried out, focused attention on the activity carried out within four projects:

1. Technosols production (Team A),
2. Operational Process for Circular Plasters Experimentation (Team A);
3. Enforced Embankment for civil applications (Team A);
4. Reuse fired ceramic into the traditional ceramic production (Team C),
5. Reuse of Hazelnut skins (HS), a by-product of hazelnut roasting, for livestock feed (Team F).

For the four projects mentioned the applicable regulations were taken into account, specifying whether they fall within the cases of End of Waste (EoW) or by-products. To this end, the regulation of EoW and by-products has been deepened.

Specifically, the activity carried out by Research Teams A and C falls under the construction EoW regulation. In this regard, the recent regulation of Ministerial Decree 127/2024 and the Declaration of Conformity of the recovered aggregate obtained at the outcome of the EoW procedure has been deepened. The activity of Team A and Team C was carried out under the validity of Ministerial Decree 152/2022, repealed by the Ministerial Decree. 127/2024. However, it was considered interesting to hypothesize the application of the new regulation to the end of waste procedures carried out.

The regulation on CE marking was then generally recalled and it was decided to focus attention on the regulation of CE marking of construction products due to the three pilot cases:

- Technosols production (Team A),
- Operational Process for Circular Plasters Experimentation (Team A),
- Enforced Embankment for civil applications (Team A);
- Reuse fired ceramic into the traditional ceramic production (Team C) - which were examined in detail.

C) BY-PRODUCTS AND EOW REGULATION

As a general principle, waste management strategies, both at the European and national levels, are based on the recovery and valorisation of the waste generated, thereby contributing to a general needs of raw materials and critical raw materials supply, integrating what exploited and processed from natural ore deposits (mining activities s.s.) [1].

The waste rules apply essentially whenever a substance qualifies as waste under art. 183 (1), point (a), and until it ceases to be such under art. 184-ter of the Legislative Decree 3 April 2006, n. 152 (hereinafter “Environmental Code”), thus being able to be freely marketed as a product: in this last case, we also talk about EoW.

There are, however, cases where a substance does not acquire the status of waste, even though it constitutes a “residue” of a production process: under certain conditions, it qualifies as a “by-product” within the meaning of Article 184-bis of the Environmental Code.

Both legal regimes (EoW and by-product) therefore have an impact on the application of the rules on waste and, consequently, on the compliance obligations incumbent upon operators in the course of their activities.

A. By-products

Where certain conditions are met, a substance or object resulting from a production process, that the primary purpose of which is not the production of that substance or object, shall not be regarded as waste; as such, it may be placed on the market without being subject to the requirements applicable to waste.

The concept of a by-product has consistently raised questions as regards the conditions set out in Article 184-bis p.1. of the Environmental Code. To dispel, at least in part, such doubts, Ministerial Decree of 13 October 2016, No. 264 (hereinafter “MD 264/16”) and the related Ministerial Interpretative Circular of 30 May 2017, protocol No. 7619 (“Circular No. 7619/2017”) were adopted.

Pursuant to Article 1, point (c) of MD 264/16, a by-product is defined as “a production residue which does not constitute waste within the meaning of Article 184-bis of Legislative Decree of 3 April 2006, No. 152”, further specifying, in the first paragraph of the following Article 4, that “materials are to be regarded as products and not as waste where the producer demonstrates that, not having been intentionally produced as the primary objective of the production cycle, they are intended for use in the same or in a subsequent process, either by the producer himself or by third parties.” By-products are therefore residues which the producer does not intend to discard and which are generated by a production process of which they are not the principal product. The legislator further subjects the classification as a by-product to the cumulative fulfilment, by the producer, of the conditions laid down in Article 184-bis of the Environmental Code.

One of the most critical aspects relating to the qualification of by-products concerns the notion of “normal industrial practice”: in this regard, Article 6 of MD 264/16 provides a dual definition, both negative and positive. Paragraph 1 stipulates that “processes and operations necessary to ensure that the environmental characteristics of the substance or object meet, for the specific use, all relevant requirements concerning products, the protection of health and the environment, and that do not lead to overall negative environmental impacts, shall not constitute normal industrial practice, unless they are carried out within the same production cycle, in accordance with paragraph 2”; paragraph 2 further provides that “activities and operations that form an integral part of the production cycle of the residue shall, in any case, fall within normal industrial practice, even if designed and implemented for the specific purpose of ensuring that the environmental or health characteristics of the substance or object meet all relevant requirements concerning products, the protection of health and the environment, and do not lead to overall negative environmental impacts.”

Circular No. 7619/2017, in turn, illustrates the two prevailing approaches in case-law: for the purpose

of demonstrating that the operation falls within 'normal industrial practice', the operator may prove, by way of example, that:

- the treatment does not affect or cause the material to lose its identity, commercial characteristics or environmental quality, does not cause a structural alteration of the chemical-physical components of the substance or in its radical transformation (Cass. pen. n. 40109/2015 and Cass. pen. n. 17453/2012);
- the treatment corresponds to the operations ordinarily carried out in the production process in which the material is used, and in particular to those ordinarily performed on the raw material which the by-product replaces (Cass. pen. n. 17453/2012; Cass. pen. n. 20886/2013).

In any case, case-law remains closely linked to the examination of the specific circumstances of each individual case. A useful reference tool is the website <https://www.elencosottoprodotti.it>; in this regard, it should be noted that the register does not constitute an enabling requirement for producers or users of by-products, but serves solely for information purposes and to facilitate exchanges.

The qualification of a material as a by-product, and therefore not as waste, is independent of the producer's or user's registration in the abovementioned list. This qualification is of an objective nature and is determined by demonstrating compliance with the requirements laid down in Article 184-bis of Legislative Decree No. 152/2006. Accordingly, inclusion in the register by the producer or user, in itself, is not sufficient to qualify a residue as a by-product; conversely, failure to register does not automatically result in the classification of the residue as waste.

B. End of Waste (EoW)

Article 184-ter of the Environmental Code also provides for the End of Waste (EoW), in implementation of Directive 2008/98/EC, namely the "cessation of waste status" which substantially corresponds to what, under the previous Article 181-bis of the same Code, was referred to as the production of "secondary raw materials." A waste ceases to be waste because, through a dedicated industrial process, it is reprocessed into a product that is freely marketable and usable. The resulting product has a market value and can be managed without the restrictions and formalities applicable to waste.

In order to prevent speculative fraud, this operation must be strictly regulated, and the conditions under which it may take place must be precisely defined. As regards detailed rules, in the absence of EU provisions, the Directive leaves Member States free, in principle, to provide either through general measures (ministerial decrees) or even on a "case-by-case" basis.

Following Directive (EU) 2018/851 of 30 May 2018, which, in the framework of measures aimed at promoting the so-called circular economy [2], amended Article 6 of Directive 2008/98, the Italian legislator, through Decree-Law of 3 September 2019 No. 101, converted into Law of 2 November 2019 No. 128, amended national provisions by expressly introducing the possibility of determining, on a "case-by-case" basis (and not only by means of general ministerial decrees), the criteria under which the material processed in a specific facility loses its waste status, in order to foster the development of pilot facilities based on innovative technologies.

Therefore, the specific criteria for recognising EoW may be established either by EU legislation or, in its absence, by the Member States, through general measures (ministerial decrees) or on a "case-by-case" basis, in the framework of issuing the Integrated Environmental Authorisation or the authorisations referred to in Articles 208, 209 and 211 of the Environmental Code [3].

During the preliminary phase, the competent authorities must refer, in addition to the conditions laid down in Article 184-ter (1), the "detailed criteria" referred to in Article 184-ter(3) of Legislative Decree 152/2006.

At Union level, End-of-Waste (EoW) criteria have been established by means of specific

Regulations for the following materials:

- iron, steel and aluminium – Regulation (EU) No. 333/2011;
- glass cullet – Regulation (EU) No. 1179/2012;
- copper and copper alloys – Regulation (EU) No. 715/2013.

At national level, six Ministerial Decrees have been adopted regulating EoW criteria for specific waste streams:

- Ministerial Decree of 14 February 2013, No. 22 (**solid recovered fuel**);
- Ministerial Decree of 28 March 2018, No. 69 (**bituminous conglomerate**);
- Ministerial Decree of 15 May 2019, No. 62 (**absorbent hygiene products**);
- Ministerial Decree of 31 March 2020, No. 78 (**recycled rubber from end-of-life tyres**);
- Ministerial Decree of 22 September 2020, No. 188 (**paper and cardboard**);
- Ministerial Decree of 27 September 2022, No. 152 (**construction and demolition waste**), repealed and replaced by Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024.

As regards “case-by-case” authorisations, since 30 September 2021 the RECER system is operational: this is the National Register for the collection of authorisations granted and the outcomes of simplified procedures concluded for the purpose of carrying out waste recovery operations. RECER is divided into two sections: one dedicated to ordinary authorisations, i.e. measures adopted pursuant to Articles 208, 209 and 211 and Title III-bis of Part Two of Legislative Decree No. 152/2006 (Integrated Environmental Authorisation – AIA); the other dedicated to the outcomes of simplified procedures, pursuant to Articles 214 and 216 of the same Decree. This national database is intended to ensure compliance with the principles of transparency and public accessibility of authorisations, and to provide as complete a picture as possible of the facilities carrying out waste recovery, thereby facilitating monitoring and control activities.

D) EoW CONSTRUCTION and DEMOLITION WASTE: D.M. 127/2024

The production of special waste from construction and demolition activities - CDW - represents a significant percentage of the quantity of special waste produced annually in Italy and Europe.

In Italy the percentage of non-hazardous special waste for construction and demolition is equal to approximately 50% of the total non-hazardous special waste (4). In Europe, total waste production in 2022, including household waste, amounted to approximately 2.2 billion tonnes, with the percentage of construction and demolition waste equal to 38,4% of the total (5).

As a general rule, in the case of residues from C&D an assessment is carried out to verify, from a circular economy perspective, whether residues from **C&D** can be considered as (a) **by-products to be reused and not waste to be subjected to recovery or disposal** or (b) **waste (CDW) to be subjected to recovery or disposal**.

With regard to the assessment of residues from **C&D as by-products**, it must be recalled the absence of specific rules establishing conditions, criteria and limits similar to those present in the regulations for the End of Waste, with the consequence that the burden of proof and the risks of incurring heavy penalties have almost always induced the producers/holders of residues from C&D not to qualify (and use) them as by-products, but as waste (6).

Because of the absence of specific criteria for the qualification of residues from C&D as by-

products, the general criteria provided for in Art. 184-bis of Legislative Decree no. 152/2006 and the criteria contained in Ministerial Decree no. 246/2016 (Regulation containing indicative criteria to facilitate the demonstration of the existence of the requirements for the qualification of production residues as by-products and not as waste) must be applied.

Usually criminal jurisprudence has considered the qualification of the C&D residue as a by-product an exception to its qualification as waste. It must be mentioned the well-established guideline (See Cass. pen., section III, No 18020/2024) according to which demolition materials could never be considered by-products, regardless of their re-use, even if certain. The aforementioned position is based on a previous guideline (See Cass. pen., section III, 28 July 2015, n. 33028) according to which “demolition materials are always waste and remain so until, if necessary, they are the subject of a recovery process”, because “the demolition of a building (13), which can take place for different reasons, is not aimed at the production of anything, but rather to the elimination of the building itself, nor can it take on relevance ... the fact that the demolition is aimed at the construction of a new building, which cannot be considered the final product of demolition, as this activity does not constitute the precursor to a construction, which can also be carried out independently of previous demolitions”.

The path of qualifying residues from **C&D as waste (CDW) to be subjected to recovery with the indication of the criteria for the cessation of the waste qualification, in accordance with the criteria of the EoW** set by Art. 184 ter of Legislative Decree 152/2006, was undertaken with the approval of the first EoW decree for inert construction and demolition waste and for other inert waste of mineral origin, the Ministerial Decree of 27 September 2022, no. 152, which went into effect on November 4, 2022.

Ministerial Decree 152/2022 [7] was repealed by Ministerial Decree 127/2024, which will be effective from 8 January 2026.

Recently the Council of State (Sect. IV, 11 July 2025, n. 6062) specified that “a waste ends to be such because, through a specific industrial process, it is re-transformed into a product, freely marketable and usable. It is, as is evident, a result of economic interest, because the product thus obtained on the one hand has a market value, while on the other hand it can be treated without the precautions and formalities required for waste”.

In the light of the case-law, it may be observed that the end of waste, or, according to the heading of Article 184 ter of Legislative Decree No 152/2006, the “cessation of the classification of waste” is a concept which substantially coincides with that which in the force of Article 181 of Legislative Decree No 152/2006 was known as the production of “secondary raw materials”.

Pursuant to Ministerial Decree 127/2024, the outcome of the re-transformation process following which the waste ends to be waste to take on the characteristics of a marketable and usable product is defined “recovered aggregate”.

The Ministerial Decree is made up of 9 articles and 3 technical Annexes that define the process, quality and compliance requirements for the production of recycled aggregates.

Ministerial Decree 127/2024 establishes the technical criteria and environmental conditions according to which certain inert waste ends to be considered as such to become products in all respects, ready to be reintroduced on the market, acquiring the status of “End of Waste”, i.e. recovered aggregates suitable to replace natural raw materials.

The main purpose of the decree, pursuant to Article 1 (1), is to establish, in accordance with Article 184-ter of Legislative Decree 152/2006, “the specific criteria in respect of which inert waste from construction and demolition activities (C&D) and other inert waste of mineral origin, as defined in Article 2 (1) (a) and (b), and listed in Tables 1 and 2 of Annex 1, end to be classified as waste following suitable recovery operations” and can be transformed into usable and marketable products.

Article 1 (2) delimits the scope of the regulation, specifying that where recovery operations involve waste other than that listed in paragraph 1, or provide for different uses from those indicated in

Article 4 and Annex 2, the processing cannot take place according to the general rules of the decree, but must follow the procedure “case by case”, provided for in Article 184-ter (3) of Legislative Decree. 152/2006. The decree makes it clear that these exceptions must remain residual and cannot be used to circumvent the standardized conditions of the regulation.

Article 2 of Ministerial Decree 127/2024 incorporates many definitions already introduced by the Ministerial Decree. 152/2022.

Among these, the definition of inert waste is particularly important, understood as “*solid waste deriving from construction and demolition activities or from other mineral sources, which does not undergo significant physical, chemical or biological transformations, does not dissolve, does not burn, are not subject to dangerous reactions, are not biodegradable and, in case of contact with other materials, they do not generate harmful effects that cause pollution or damage to human health*”.

In line with the UNI technical standards on aggregates, the decree introduces two new definitions specifying the types of materials obtained from recovery: (i) *recycled aggregate*: aggregate of a mineral nature obtained from the recovery of inorganic waste already used in the building or infrastructure sector; (ii) *artificial aggregate*: mineral material deriving from the recovery of waste generated by industrial processes involving thermal or other modifications.

Recycled aggregate and *artificial aggregate* fall into the unified category of “*recovered aggregate*”. The decree also introduced the definition of “*batch of recovered aggregate*”, that is, a maximum quantity equal to 3,000 cubic meters of homogeneous material, useful for the application of quality controls and for the traceability of production flows.

The transformation from waste to recovered aggregate is subject to compliance with the requirements set out in Annex 1 of the Ministerial Decree. These requirements shall be:

- a. types of waste eligible for treatment (identified through EER codes);
- b. verification methods on incoming waste to ensure the absence of contaminants that are not compatible with recovery;
- c. processing operating methods necessary to obtain a product compliant with the required standards;
- d. quality requirements for the final material and the regulatory references for the CE marking, which are indispensable for placing on the market as a product.

The result of failure to comply with one or more of the above requirements is the impossibility of attributing product status to the material; in this case, in fact, the material remains a waste in all respects, with the consequent application of the relative regulations.

Ministerial Decree 127/2024 identifies the types of non-hazardous waste that can be subjected to recovery operations to obtain recovered aggregates (list in Table 1), divided into two macro-categories: (i) inert waste from construction and demolition activities (CDW); (ii) inert waste of mineral origin. The following are expressly excluded: (a) inert waste buried; (b) waste identified by EER code 170504 (excavation earth and rocks) from contaminated sites undergoing remediation proceedings.

Wastes eligible for the production of recovered aggregate are shown in Table 1:

(i) Inert waste from construction and demolition (CDW) activities:

- 170101 Cement
- 170102 Bricks

- 170103 Tiles and ceramics
- 170107 Mixtures or slag of cement, bricks, tiles and ceramics, other than 170106
- 170302 Bituminous mixtures, excluding those containing tar (170301)
- 170504 Excavation earths and rocks, other than 170503 (containing dangerous substances)
- 170508 Rockstone for railway ballasts, other than that referred to in heading 170507
- 170904 Mixed construction and demolition waste, other than that referred to in headings 170901, 170902 and 170903 containing dangerous substances.

(ii) Inert waste of mineral origin:

- 010408 Gravel and crushed stone waste, other than that referred to in heading 010407, containing dangerous substances
- 010409 Sand and clay waste
- 010410 Dusts and similar residues, other than those referred to in heading 010407
- 010413 Waste produced by cutting and sawing stone, other than that referred to in heading 010407
- 101201 Preparation mixture residues not subjected to heat treatment
- 101206 Waste moulds consisting exclusively of scraps and scraps of glazed and fired raw ceramic products or of scraps of fired brick and expanded clay possibly covered with raw enamel in a concentration < 10% by weight
- 101208 Waste ceramics, bricks, tiles and building materials (subjected to heat treatment)
- 101311 Waste from the production of cement-based composite materials, other than those referred to in headings 101309 and 101310, containing dangerous substances
- 120117 Residues of sandblasting material, other than those referred to in heading 120116 consisting exclusively of waste abrasive sands
- 191209 Minerals (for example, sand, rocks, aggregates)
- 200301 Unseparated municipal waste, limited to the inert fraction of abandoned waste from construction and demolition activities.

Point (b) of Annex 1 to Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024 lays down the procedures for the verification and acceptance of incoming waste at plants authorised to produce recovered aggregates.

Each waste load must undergo three levels of control: a documentary check upon arrival, a visual inspection carried out by qualified personnel, and, where necessary, supplementary checks. The producer shall adopt a formalised procedure to ensure that the characteristics of the waste are in compliance with regulatory requirements. The obligation to fill in the Waste Identification Form (FIR), jointly signed by both producer and transporter, remains unaffected.

Point (c) of Annex 1 regulates the minimum treatment operations required for waste to cease being waste and become recovered aggregate.

The treatment process includes mechanical operations such as, by way of example, crushing, screening/granulometric selection, and separation of undesired fractions.

Compared to Ministerial Decree No. 152/2022, the term “grinding” has been replaced by “crushing”. The decree clarifies that, in line with Article 184-ter of the Environmental Code, recovery may also consist solely in verifying compliance with the relevant criteria. It also governs the management of temporary storage of recovered material at the treatment facility where it was produced, requiring that, for the entire period during which the recovered aggregate remains at the plant, the material must be stored and handled within the plant and in designated storage areas.

Point (d) of Annex 1 defines the control activities to be carried out on the outgoing aggregates, distinguishing two separate areas:

d1) Analytical testing of recovered aggregate batches “as produced”;

d2) Leaching tests to verify compliance with the limit values laid down in Table 3, to be performed according to UNI 10802 and UNI EN 12457-2 standards.

One of the main innovations of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024 is the adjustment of the concentration limits in Table 2 of Annex 1, depending on the intended uses listed in Annex 2. This addresses concerns raised by stakeholders regarding the overly restrictive criteria applicable to “as produced” materials (point d1) under the previous regulation, which hindered practical implementation of the rules.

Specifically, more stringent limits are now set for aggregates intended for environmental recovery, embankments, and fillings.

For other uses—such as embankment bodies for civil engineering works, road, railway and airport sub-bases, foundation layers, bituminous mixtures, hydraulically bound mixtures or concrete production—less stringent (environmental) limits are applied.

Furthermore, for batches of recovered aggregate destined for clinker or cement production, only the asbestos concentration limit (100 mg/kg, dry substance) is considered.

Article 4 of the Decree defines the specific uses for which recovered aggregates may be employed, by referring to Annex 2, which provides an exhaustive list of permitted uses.

Compared to the previous regulation (Ministerial Decree No. 152/2022), Annex 2 has been expanded and clarified, introducing new fields of application. The permitted uses of recovered aggregate include:

- a) Environmental recovery, embankments, and fillings;
- b) Construction of embankment bodies for civil engineering works;
- c) Production of bituminous mixtures, road, railway, and airport sub-bases, and paving of civil and industrial yards;
- d) Foundation layers for transport infrastructure and yards;
- e) Ancillary layers with draining, frost-resistant, or anti-capillary functions;
- f) Production of hydraulically bound mixtures, such as cement-treated and pumpable mixtures;
- g) Concrete production.

Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024 introduces the use of recovered aggregates for the production of cement clinker (new point h Annex 2) and cement (new point l Annex 2).

Additionally, the use of recovered aggregates for hydraulically bound mixtures and concrete production, already provided for in Ministerial Decree No. 152/2022, is now divided into two distinct categories, for the “packaging of legal mixtures with hydraulic binders” (for example cement

mixtures and concrete mixes) and for the "packaging of concrete", that reflecting the practical need to promote actual reuse across a wide range of construction and infrastructure applications.

Based on feedback collected during the drafting process, Table 5 has been updated to list the reference technical standards for the various uses of recovered aggregates. The regulation specifies that the most up-to-date versions of the technical standards must be applied.

As for the use in clinker production (new point h), due to the absence of standardised technical specifications at the time of the decree's publication, Table 6 introduces performance criteria for recovered aggregates intended for such use.

Articles 5 and 6 set out the responsibilities of the producer of recovered aggregates, introducing certain simplifications compared to Ministerial Decree No. 152/2022.

Article 5 requires that, upon completion of the recovery process, the producer shall prepare a declaration of conformity, in the format set out in Annex 3, certifying compliance with all criteria necessary for the waste to lose its status, as laid down in Article 3 and Annex 1. This declaration: i) must be submitted, also cumulatively, within six months of production, to the competent authority and the regional environmental protection agency (ARPA/APPA); ii) must be kept for five years, including in digital format, at the plant or registered office, and made available in case of inspection.

For traceability purposes, the producer must take a representative sample of each batch, in accordance with UNI 10802 and, where necessary, UNI/TR 11682, and keep it for at least one year. Under the previous decree, the retention period was five years. Exemptions apply to undertakings registered under Regulation (EC) No 1221/2009 (EMAS) or certified under UNI EN ISO 14001 by an accredited body.

Article 6 introduces the obligation for producers to establish an internal management system ensuring: continuous quality control of the material produced; a self-monitoring mechanism to verify compliance with the decree's criteria.

A key innovation by Decree No. 127/2024, compared to Ministerial Decree No. 152/2022, is the removal of the requirement for a UNI EN ISO 9001-certified system. Equivalent procedures—also through recognised accreditation systems—are now deemed sufficient, thus facilitating compliance for small and medium-sized enterprises.

Article 8 of Decree No. 127/2024 provides that all operators of treatment facilities handling the waste types listed in Table 1 of Annex 1 and intended for the uses listed in Annex 2, must submit, within 180 days of the decree's entry into force (i.e., by 25 March 2025), an application to amend their existing authorisation to the competent authority. Failure to submit such an application would prevent the production of recovered aggregates under the new End-of-Waste rules.

The main innovations introduced by Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, addressing criticalities raised by trade associations, include: inclusion of abandoned construction and demolition waste (CDW) among the admissible inputs for recycled aggregate production; addition of waste code 200301, relating to unsorted municipal waste, limited to the inert fraction of abandoned waste from construction and demolition activities; redefinition of environmental and technical criteria based on end use, in line with UNI standards and principles of reasonableness and proportionality, also endorsed by the Council of State; differentiation of limit values (for aromatics, PAHs, hydrocarbons >C12, phenol, PCBs, Cr VI) depending on end use; modification of certain sampling methods, now aligned with more appropriate reference technical standards; simplification of administrative obligations, especially regarding the biannual submission of conformity declarations to ARPA and the competent authority; increased chloride and sulphate limits for leaching tests, compared to the overly restrictive values laid down in Ministerial Decree of 5 February 1998.

By promoting the recovery of inert materials and encouraging the use of recovered aggregates, Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024 aligns with the objectives of the Minimum Environmental Criteria (CAM), in particular the CAM for Buildings (Decree of 23/06/2022) and the CAM for Roads (Decree of

05/08/2024), which mandate the use of sustainable materials in public works procurement in order to support a circular economy and reduce the environmental impact of construction activities.

E) PILOT CASES: POSSIBLE APPLICATIONS OF THE END-OF-WASTE (EoW) PROCESSES PURSUANT TO MINISTERIAL DECREE NO. 127/2024 – Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) and Extractive Waste (EER 010413)

Following the presentation of the provisions laid down in Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, a number of projects developed under RM1 are examined, specifically the projects concerning: (i) the **production of technosols**, (ii) the testing process for **circular plasters** and (iii) the production of **enforced embankments for civil application** (Team A) (see Deliverable D1.3), with the aim of assessing the potential applicability of the current rules laid down in Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024 to the activities carried out under the aforementioned projects.

It should be noted, as a preliminary matter, that the activities carried out within the projects under review were conducted in accordance with the legislation in force at the time of project implementation, i.e. Ministerial Decree No. 152/2022, which has since been repealed by the current Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024.

i) **Pilot case Production of technosols: hypothesis of application of Ministerial Decree 127/2024**

The studied process involved the production of technosols (artificial new soils) using different materials and intentionally modelling them to provide suitable materials for urban greenery, to prevent erosion and floods or for to rehabilitate and regenerate urban, industrial or contaminated/degraded areas. The herein technosols can be defined as a man-made soil constituted of various materials (urban/industrial wastes, natural materials, deep horizons soils, etc...) that contribute in boosting circular economy, favoring ground stability/site rehabilitation and enhancing urban landscape.

For the process, the waste inorganic materials were collected from a treatment plant which processes natural aggregates, CDW, excavated rocks and soils. The organic materials were provided by a local composting plant.

In all combinations they were used:

- 1) CDW: recovered aggregates (fine fraction) produced from the plant (0-5.6 mm) after some simple phases of collection of CDW, removal of unwanted materials (e.g., wood, plastic) and crushing and sieving phases;
- 2) Compost produced from the organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OFMSW) and green mulched residues;
- 3) Excavated natural soil, sieved at 5.6 mm to exclude larger particles that could change the comparability with the recovered CDW.

The use of recycled aggregates from CDW combined with excavated natural soil for the production of technosols may be brought within the scope of application of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, as it appears to fall within the relevant specific criteria.

With reference to Table 1 of Annex 1 to Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, which sets out the list of waste types admissible for End-of-Waste processes, the appropriate European Waste Code (EWC) to be assigned to the component consisting of CDW – recovered aggregates – is 170904. This is the same EWC code provided under the previous Ministerial Decree No. 152/2022.

As regards the parameters to be tested and the limit values of chemical substances (e.g. asbestos, benzene, styrene, xylene, etc.) indicated in Table 2, it should be noted that, in line with the

innovation introduced by Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, the limit concentrations for the use of chemical substances now vary according to the intended use, unlike the previous regime, which made no such distinctions for aggregates obtained through the End-of-Waste process.

With regard to the use of technosol as envisaged in the project, this can, in abstract terms, be traced back to point (a) of Annex 2, which refers to environmental recovery, fillings and embankments (in particular, under the item “environmental recovery”).

It should be emphasised that, for the use of technosol, the limit concentrations for chemical substances allowed for such use have to be referred to the uses under points (a) of Annex 2.

As regards the technical standards for the use of recovered aggregates (Table 5 of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024), the use as technosol under real conditions could fall under the category “environmental recovery, fillings and embankments”, for which compliance with UNI EN 13242 is required (column 2 of Table 5). This is the same standard, as previously noted, applicable to CE marking under Table 4 of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024. For technical suitability, UNI 11531-1, Table 4a shall be applied.

In this respect, it should be noted that Regulation (EU) No 2011/305 has been repealed by Regulation (EU) 2024/3110 which will be effective from 8 January 2026.

Before proceeding, it is important to verify the applicable regulations currently in force in Italy as for technosols application, where, at present, no specific national regulations is in force. Therefore, their application should follow the general legal framework established by Legislative Decree 152/2006 regarding the clean-up of polluted sites. In particular, Legislative Decree 152/2006 establishes the threshold concentration limits for contamination of pollutants in the soil and subsoil based on the specific intended use indicated in Table 1 of Annex 5 to Part IV of the Legislative Decree. 152/2006. For technosol, therefore, in the absence of specific legislation, the threshold concentrations of contamination of pollutants indicated in the aforementioned Table 1 of Annex 5 should be respected, where it is distinguished with regard to the concentrations between the use of soil for public, private and residential green use (column A) and destination of soil for commercial and industrial use (column B).

However, since there is no regulation that clearly defines the origin or types of materials that can be used to create technosols, their application becomes challenging if one intends to follow the current legislation strictly. This regulatory gap complicates the development and standardized implementation of technosols in practice.

ii) Pilot case Operational Process for Circular Plasters Experimentation: hypothesis of application of Ministerial Decree 127/2024 to the production of circular mortars

The operational process carried out by Team A for testing circular plasters involved a structured approach to ensure in-depth assessment of the material and optimised performance.

In the initial phase, an analysis was carried out on the input materials: quarry waste fine sludge (EER 010413), rice husk, hemp, and cork chips. Each material underwent rigorous chemical, physical and microstructural testing, including XRD, XRF, SEM, FT-IR, and particle size analysis. These tests aimed to verify the suitability of the materials for sustainable and effective plaster formulations.

Based on the input material properties, various mixtures were prepared by adjusting the proportions of lime, quarry dust and organic components. The aim was to identify optimal combinations that balanced workability, strength, and environmental sustainability. The operational process thus aimed to develop sustainable construction materials, combining traditional craftsmanship with modern testing methodologies. It aligns with the principles of the circular economy, promoting innovative and environmentally friendly solutions for the construction sector.

The testing activity on circular plasters using quarry waste dust combined with rice husk, hemp and cork chips can be regarded as falling within the scope of application of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, as it meets the specific criteria laid down therein.

With regard to Table 1 of Annex 1 of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, listing admissible waste types for the End-of-Waste process, the EWC code to be assigned to the component consisting of quarry waste dust is 010413. This is the same code provided under the previous Ministerial Decree No. 152/2022. As for the use of the mixtures obtained by adjusting the ratios of lime, quarry dust and organic components—the so-called “circular plasters”—for the purpose of producing sustainable construction materials, such use can, in abstract terms, be traced back to point (f) of Annex 2, relating to the production of mixtures bound with hydraulic binders.

As regards the parameters to be tested and the limit values of chemical substances (e.g. asbestos, benzene, styrene, xylene, etc.) in Table 2, it must again be noted that the concentration limits now vary depending on the intended use, in contrast to the previous regulatory framework, which did not allow for differentiated limits based on use.

With reference to the technical standards for CE marking (Table 4 of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024), the applicable standard for circular plasters is UNI EN 13139, concerning Aggregates for mortar (also required under the previous Ministerial Decree No. 152/2022).

As regards the technical standards for the use of circular plasters (Table 5 of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024) under the category “production of mixtures bound with hydraulic binders”, reference should be made to the standards in column 2 of Table 5: UNI EN 13242, and, under Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, also UNI EN 13139 and UNI EN 13055.

For technical suitability, the applicable standards (column 3 of Table 5) are: UNI EN 14227-1, UNI 11531-2, UNI EN 998-1, UNI EN 998-2, and UNI 11104 Type B, the latter three having been introduced by Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024.

Lastly, Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024 reiterates that CE marking must be applied to all uses, pursuant to Regulation (EU) No 305/2011. As already mentioned, that regulation has been repealed by Regulation (EU) 2024/3110, applicable from 7 January 2025.

iii) Pilot case Production of enforced embankments for civil applications: hypothesis of application of Ministerial Decree 127/2024

The studied process involved the production of enforced embankments for civil applications using waste inorganic materials collected from a treatment plant which processes natural aggregates, CDW, excavation rocks and soils.

In particular, the project involved the use of recycled aggregates from CDW combined with excavated soils, reinforced with geogrids. Regarding the performance of recycled materials it was noted that the Recycled aggregates from C&D waste exhibited comparable performance to conventional materials. Finally the materials achieved contributed to environmental sustainability and resource recovery.

The study provided the first empirical evidence supporting the use of recycled aggregates in reinforced embankments under real-world conditions.

The use of recycled aggregates from construction and demolition waste (C&DW) combined with excavated soil for the production of enforced embankments may be brought within the scope of application of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, as it appears to fall within the relevant specific criteria.

With reference to Table 1 of Annex 1 to Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, which sets out the list of waste types admissible for End-of-Waste processes, the appropriate European Waste Code (EWC) to be assigned to the component consisting of C&DW – recovered aggregates – is 170904. This is the same EWC code provided under the previous Ministerial Decree No. 152/2022.

As regards the parameters to be tested and the limit values of chemical substances (e.g. asbestos, benzene, styrene, xylene, etc.) indicated in Table 2, it should be noted that, in line with the innovation introduced by Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, the limit concentrations for the use of chemical substances now vary according to the intended use, unlike the previous regime, which made no such distinctions for aggregates obtained through the End-of-Waste process.

With regard to the use of reinforced embankments under real conditions, this can, in abstract terms, be traced back to point (b) of Annex 2, which refers to Construction of embankment bodies for civil engineering works.

It should be emphasised that, for the use of recovered aggregate, i.e. in reinforced embankments under real-world conditions, the limit concentrations for chemical substances allowed for such use are higher, and therefore more favourable. See the second column referring to the uses under points (b) to (g) of Annex 2.

With reference to the technical standards for CE marking (Table 4 of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024), the applicable technical standard should be UNI EN 13242, concerning Aggregates for unbound and hydraulically bound materials for use in civil engineering work and road construction (the same standard provided under the previous Ministerial Decree No. 152/2022).

As regards the technical standards for the use of recovered aggregates (Table 5 of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024), the use in reinforced embankments under real conditions would fall under the category "Construction of embankment bodies for civil engineering works", for which compliance with UNI EN 13242 is required (column 2 of Table 5). This is the same standard, as previously noted, applicable to CE marking under Table 4 of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024. For technical suitability, UNI 11531-1, Table 4a shall apply.

Lastly, Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024 specifies that CE marking must be applied for all uses, in accordance with Regulation (EU) No 2011/305 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 laying down harmonised conditions for the marketing of construction products.

In this respect, it should be noted that Regulation (EU) No 2011/305 has been repealed by Regulation (EU) 2024/3110 –which will be effective from 8 January 2026.

F) CASE STUDY: POSSIBLE APPLICATIONS OF THE END-OF-WASTE (EoW) PROCESSES PURSUANT TO MINISTERIAL DECREE NO. 127/2024 – Ceramic Waste

Case study Reuse of fired ceramic scraps into the traditional ceramic production: hypothesis of application of Ministerial Decree 127/2024

The project was aimed at evaluate the feasibility of reuse of different type sof waste into the traditional ceramic production. The first type of investigated waste material was represented by fired ceramic scraps (hereafter FCS). FCS were introduced in the sanitary-ware slip formulation at different levels (6, 12, 15, 18 and 21 wt. %) at the expense of natural raw materials such as feldspar and quartz.

The technological properties of the ceramic body were generally maintained (rheology, WA, shrinkage, mechanical resistance) or improved (deformation) with the exception of the thermal dilation, which was reduced compared to the reference formulation.

Waste from ceramic processing may be brought within the scope of application of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, as it meets the relevant specific criteria.

With regard to Table 1 of Annex 1 to Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, concerning the waste types admissible for End-of-Waste (EoW) processes, the appropriate European Waste Code (EWC) to be assigned to the component consisting of fired ceramic scrap (FCS) is 101208. This is the same code previously provided under Ministerial Decree No. 152/2022.

As regards the parameters to be tested and the limit values for chemical substances (e.g. asbestos, benzene, styrene, xylene, etc.) indicated in Table 2, it should be noted that, pursuant to the changes introduced by Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, the limit concentrations for chemical substances now vary depending on the intended use of the recovered aggregate. This represents a departure from the previous legal framework, which did not make such distinctions between different uses of recovered aggregates derived from the EoW process.

The use of aggregates recovered through the treatment and recovery of fired ceramic scrap may, in abstract terms, be traced back to point (f) of Annex 2, relating to the production of mixtures bound with hydraulic binders.

In this respect, it should be emphasised that, for uses falling under point (f) of Annex 2—production of mixtures bound with hydraulic binders—the limit concentrations for chemical substances are higher, and therefore more favourable. See the second column of Table 2, relating to uses referred to under points (b) to (g) of Annex 2.

With reference to the technical standards for CE marking (Table 4 of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024), UNI EN 13242 may apply to recovered aggregates.

As regards the technical standards applicable to the use of the recovered aggregate for the production of mixtures bound with hydraulic binders (as per the scenario considered), reference should be made to Table 5, column 2, which includes UNI EN 13242 and, pursuant to Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, also UNI EN 13139 and UNI EN 13055. For technical suitability, compliance is required with the standards listed in column 3 of Table 5, namely: UNI EN 14227-1, UNI 11531-2, UNI EN 998-1, UNI EN 998-2, and UNI 11104 Type B. The standards UNI 11531-2, UNI EN 998-1, and UNI EN 998-2 were introduced by Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024.

Pursuant to Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024, recovered aggregates may only be used for the specific purposes listed in Annex 2. In the present case, where recovered aggregate from fired ceramic scrap is used for one of the specific purposes listed in the said Annex (e.g. production of mixtures bound with hydraulic binders such as cement-bound mixtures or concreteable mixes), the technical standards set out in Table 5 must be complied with.

Conversely, if the aggregate is used for purposes other than those listed in Article 4 of Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024 (which refers to Annex 2), the corresponding recovery operations shall be subject to case-by-case authorisation, pursuant to Article 184-ter(3) of Legislative Decree No. 152/2006.

F) PILOT CASE REUSE OF HAZELNUT ROASTING FOR LIVESTOCK FEED: BY-PRODUCT REGULATION

The research project of Team F dealt with the reuse of food supply by-products for livestock feed, focusing attention on the by-product of hazelnut roasting represented by hazelnut skin.

Hazelnut skins (HS), a by-product of hazelnut roasting, are nutritionally valuable, containing fiber, unsaturated fatty acids, phenolic compounds, and tocopherols, which provide antioxidant effects.

This project aimed to explore the use of hazelnut skins as a feeding option for beef cattle, promoting the sustainability of agricultural practices, in line with the principles of the circular economy.

The reuse of hazelnut roasting by-products, in particular hazelnut skins, for animal feed purposes falls within the scope of Article 184-bis of Legislative Decree No. 152/2006.

As recalled above, in order for production residues to be considered by-products rather than waste, the following conditions must be fulfilled: i) the substance or object results from a production process, of which it is an integral part, and the primary purpose of which is not the production of

that substance or object; ii) it is certain that the substance or object will be used during the same or a subsequent production process by the producer or by third parties; iii) the substance or object can be used directly without any further treatment, other than normal industrial practice; iv) the further use is lawful, meaning that the substance or object meets, for the specific use, all relevant product, health and environmental protection requirements, and will not lead to overall adverse environmental or human health impacts.

The Ministry of the Environment, through the adoption of Ministerial Decree No. 264/2016 and the Circular of 30 May 2017, laid down indicative criteria to facilitate the demonstration of compliance with the requirements for the classification of production residues as by-products rather than waste.

Pursuant to Article 1(c) of Ministerial Decree No. 264/2016, a by-product is defined as “a production residue which does not constitute waste within the meaning of Article 184-bis of Legislative Decree No. 152 of 3 April 2006”. Article 4(1) clarifies that “they shall be considered products and not waste when the producer demonstrates that, although they were not intentionally produced as the primary objective of the production cycle, they are intended for use in the same or a subsequent process, by the producer or by third parties”. Circular No. 7619 of 30 May 2017 from the Ministry of the Environment refers to the technical data sheet of the by-product, through which operators may demonstrate that all the requirements of Article 184-bis(1) have been met. The Circular also provides for the use of a “Declaration of Conformity”, which must be completed in the event of transfer of the by-product to ensure its compliance with both the legal requirements and the technical data sheet, whose reference details must be indicated. It should also be recalled that, where plant-based by-products are used as feed, Regulation (EC) No. 183/2005 applies, establishing requirements for feed hygiene.

G) CE MARKING: CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS AND RECOVERED AGGREGATES

In the previous sections, the EoW and by-products regulations were taken into account and then, specifically, the building EoW regulations since among the projects examined three of them dealt with EoW construction hypotheses. This section will examine the regulation of CE marking whose application is mandatory for products obtained as a result of an EoW process. Then attention will be focused on the regulations relating to the CE marking envisaged for construction products and aggregates recovered due to the results achieved within the three projects examined in this Deliverable.

When waste ceases to be waste through a specific industrial process, it is converted into a product and becomes subject to CE marking requirements, which ensure its free movement and marketing within the European Economic Area.

CE marking indicates that a product is in conformity with the applicable requirements relating to health, safety and environmental protection, and that it has undergone the appropriate conformity assessment procedure. Its purpose is to guarantee that CE-marked products meet the performance requirements laid down in harmonised technical standards.

CE marking is mandatory also for recovered aggregates. If recovered aggregates are not CE-marked, they do not lose their waste status and therefore cannot be used. Only CE-marked aggregates qualify as products and may be placed on the market or used.

At present, the conditions for placing construction products on the market and for the use of CE marking are laid down by Regulation (EU) No. 305/2011 (to be repealed and replaced by Regulation (EU) 2024/3110 as of 8 January 2026). Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024 expressly refers to this Regulation for all uses, except those explicitly exempted by the Regulation itself.

When a construction product falls within the scope of a harmonised standard or complies with a European Technical Assessment, the manufacturer shall draw up a declaration of performance upon placing the product on the market, whereby they assume responsibility for the product's

compliance with the declared performance.

The declaration of performance describes the product's performance with respect to essential characteristics, in accordance with the relevant harmonised technical specifications, and contains the information set out in Annex III to Regulation (EU) No. 305/2011. It is a prerequisite for affixing the CE marking, as it certifies that the product complies with the declared essential characteristics.

CE marking may be affixed only to those construction products for which the manufacturer has issued a declaration of performance. By affixing the CE marking, manufacturers declare that they take responsibility for the product's compliance with both the declared performance and all applicable requirements set out in the Regulation and in relevant Union harmonisation legislation.

For any construction product covered by a harmonised standard or a European Technical Assessment, CE marking is the sole marking that certifies the product's compliance with the declared performance.

Therefore, it is the manufacturer's responsibility to fulfil the obligations laid down in Regulation (EU) No. 305/2011, in order to lawfully market recovered aggregates.

Among the basic requirements for construction works, as listed in Annex I to Regulation (EU) No. 305/2011, particular attention should be paid to the "sustainable use of natural resources". Construction works must be designed, built and demolished in such a way as to ensure the sustainable use of natural resources, in particular: a) reusability or recyclability of construction works, their materials and parts after demolition; b) durability of construction works; c) use of environmentally compatible primary and secondary raw materials in construction works.

In addition to the CE marking requirement, Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024 also provides for a declaration of conformity, the format of which is set out in Annex 3 to the Decree. Through this declaration—issued as a self-certification and affidavit under Articles 46 and 47 of Presidential Decree No. 445 of 28 December 2000—the producer certifies compliance with the criteria set out in Article 3, for the purpose of cessation of waste status. The declaration must be sent to the competent authority and the territorially competent regional environmental protection agency within six months from the production date of the relevant batch of recovered aggregate, and in any case before it leaves the plant.

Depending on the intended use of the recovered aggregate, the technical standards listed in Table 5 of Annex 2 to Ministerial Decree No. 127/2024 must also be complied with.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. FERRARA, *Brown economy, green economy, blue economy: l'economia circolare e il diritto dell'ambiente*, in F. DE LEONARDIS, *Studi in tema di economia circolare*, Macerata, 2019.
- [2] F. DE LEONARDIS, *Economia circolare: saggio sui suoi diversi aspetti giuridici. Verso uno Stato circolare*, in *Dir. Amm.*, 2017, 163 ss.; ID. (a cura di), *Studi in tema di economia circolare*, Eum, Edizioni Università di Macerata, 2019; ID., voce *Economia circolare*, in *Dir. pubbl.*, 2020, 22 ss.
- [3] E. SCOTTI, *Poteri pubblici, sviluppo sostenibile ed economia circolare*, in *Dir. dell'economia*, fasc. 1/2019, 493 ss.
- [4] Cfr. ISPRA, *Rapporto Rifiuti Speciali*, Ed. 2023, in <https://www.isprambiente.gov.it/it/pubblicazioni/rapporti/rapporto-rifiuti-speciali-edizione-2023>
- [5] Cfr. [Waste statistics - Statistics Explained - Eurostat](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Waste_statistics), in https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Waste_statistics; Cfr. V. GIAMPIETRO, *End of Waste per i rifiuti inerti: secondo atto*, in *Ambiente & Sviluppo*, fasc. 10/2024, 641.

[6] V. GIAMPIETRO, *End of Waste per i rifiuti inerti: secondo atto*, cit., 641.

[7] A. CRISMANI, “*End of waste*” edilizio, in *Rivista giuridica dell’edilizia*, 2023, fasc. 5, 277 – 300.

[8] V. GIAMPIETRO, *End of Waste per i rifiuti inerti: secondo atto*, cit., 647.